

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB MOTIVATION, COMMUNICATION AND WORK RELATIONSHIP AND, SALARY AND REMUNERATION ON ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

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Organizations want to achieve successful performance in the market and if possible, to have sustainable economic growth. However, in the current state of globalization and strong competition, technology is evolving rapidly, thus making the market an unsafe environment. Business organizations need to make full use of all available resources. It is already a common fact that the human resources or staffs of an organization are a key asset to achieving success. Yet, what makes employees satisfied or motivated to achieve the planned objectives? In this research, we analyze several factors that influence employee motivation to improve their performance. Through empirical and theoretical analysis, the study will identify the relationship between employee motivation and organizational effectiveness and ultimately the improvement of organizational outcomes. The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect produced by employee motivation on organizational effectiveness. Employee motivation will involve criteria such as employee bonuses, good communication within the work premises, and

satisfaction in their workplace.

KEYWORDS:-Job Motivation, Communication and Work Relationship, Salary and Remuneration, Organizational Effectiveness.

1. Introduction

On the one hand, globalization has gradually led to market enlargement and reduction of barriers, but on the other hand, it has increased competition between business organizations. Accordingly, business organizations try to at least maintain their market share and even expand it. Above all, this is challenging entrepreneurship as business organizations have to face not only local but also foreign competitors, new technologies, and different management methods. However, this whole trend generally makes the market unpredictable. Taking into account the fact that human resources or officers of an organization are value-added and the primary and most valuable resource for an organization for both its capacity and competitive advantage (Nur & Widhi, 2019;Langat, Linge& Sikalieh,2019). First of all, it needs professionals and motivated people. Furthermore, the need has arisen for cohesive and permanent collaboration between employees and business organizations. Nevertheless, skills are needed to administer and make this human capital a generator of competitive advantage. Therefore, business organizations give special priority to flexibility within the organization, thereby creating a warm climate to enhance cooperation with and between employees. As a result of strong competition, business organizations use different strategies to host talent to the organization, attracting them and unlimited various material incentives, retaining them in the long run not only to survive in the market but also to successfully meet the added value for organizational effectiveness, both in short -term and long -term perspectives (Maria,2019; Anindya,Tohir, & Jati,2020).Thus, we recall that organizational effectiveness is a slightly complex and multidimensional issue because different interest groups have different perspectives on it concerning their position. The main role played by staff in increasing or reducing the burden of one party, globalization has gradually led to market expansion and reduction of barriers, but instead, it has increased competition between business organizations.

2. Research Objectives and Research Questions

2.1 Research Objectives

1. To evaluate the relationship between job motivation on organizational effectiveness.
2. To examine the relationship between communication and work relationship on organizational effectiveness

3. To identify the relationship between salary and remuneration on organizational effectiveness

2.2 Research Questions of the Study

Research questions in this study covered:

1. Is there any relationship between job motivations on employees' performance in manufacturing firms?
2. Is there any relationship between communication and work relationship on employees' performance in manufacturing firms?
3. Is there any relationship between salary and remuneration on employees' performance in manufacturing firms?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Job Motivation

Past studies have described job motivation as closely related to job structure and motivation. Job motivation is the emotional effect of performing various functions in performing a task. According to him, job satisfaction is directly related to employee motivation, engagement, organizational cooperation, and job performance (Febrianti, Suharto & Wachyudi,2020;Pananrangi, Lewangka & Sudirman,2020).Also, gratitude and reward are important factors for increasing employee job satisfaction and motivation, which are directly linked to organizational achievement. However, different researchers support different theories about how employees should be satisfied with their work and feel about it. Past studies have found supporting the structuring of the work environment that effective performance will lead to internal and external rewards, which in turn will result in complete job satisfaction. The results of this study recommend that to make work more interesting and challenging, which in turn, will increase internal motivation, horizontal expansion is needed, which implies an increase in activities, where employees have more tasks, thus making them feel very important (Irwan, Nujum & Mangkona,2020;Moon, Youn, Hur & Kim,2020).They may see how different parts of the job are integrated into important units, making them more proud. In this context, we should take into account vertical expansion, opening up job vacancies that involve more planning, decision-making, and problem-solving, or in other words, it increases employee autonomy. Furthermore, vertical expansion where people have a wider opportunity to talk about the things, they do also appreciate their efforts. Thus, given that interest (not interest) is the basis of external autonomy motivation, work expansion may increase internal and external autonomy motivation. In short, it increases employer autonomy, self-confidence, and job satisfaction (Malba,2020;Astuti,Shodikin & Ud-Din,2020).

3.2 Communication and Work Relationship

Proper communication and good relationships between managers and subordinates or between employees are key components for performance improvement or decline. According to some researchers, business organizations that have good communication and positive working relationships with their employees produce high levels of results (Shuriye & Wambua,2020;Ahmed,Al-Hammadi,Amri,Adnan,Asma' Binti & Rosdi,2020). Thus, how can

the climate in the organization be controlled, is there proper communication and cooperation among staff, and is the management able to handle the situation. Often, there may be strong competition between staff members. Their communication and collaboration are downgraded as poor communication which will cause conflict in the business organization and as a result, they will reduce cooperation in decision making (Kalogiannidis,2020;Edward& Calen,2020). Therefore, special priority is given to flexibility and harmony in the organization, among the working staff, and the level of cooperation between the business organization and its staff, to achieve results. However, is the business organization able to manage good communication at all times with its employees? Based on previous studies found that misunderstandings often occur because the needs and capacity of staff to adapt to change are not fully understood. No clear communication was achieved with employees about the nature and importance of change. Employees, their work environment, values, norms, and customs are often ignored and disrespected (Ivanytska, Galayda & Tenytska,2018);Ahmad, Soleh, Noviantoro& Putrafinaldo,2020;Maidiyanto,Asmui & Sompaa,2020).

3.3 Salary and Remunerations

Currently, each work or service is provided at a certain price, and the price of the service follows the consolidation trend regardless of the supplier company. The same goes for employees. They strive to earn a reasonable salary in the labor market and at the same time, they want to feel qualified for the work they do. Money is a basic incentive for people. It has a dominant position over other drivers and has the magical power to retain and motivate people for higher performance, without neglecting other motivational values and incentives (Onyancha, Elijah& Muturi,2019;Darmawan,2020). Past studies have shown that job satisfaction is a pleasant or positive emotional state resulting from a person’s job evaluation or work experience, while and consider salary satisfaction as a multidimensional concept. Focusing also on the literature mentioned above, salary and motivation are external motivators; Thus, satisfaction is not derived from the activity itself but from external consequences that urge increased activity and fulfillment of objectives. These aspects bring pleasure to the employees, which directly affect the improvement of employee performance (Ahmad,2019;Wijaya& Rezeki,2020). Salaries and bonuses are instruments in the hands of managers that contribute to the effectiveness of a company, influencing the behavior of individuals or groups. Therefore, business organizations use money, bonuses, promotions, or other methods to encourage improved employer performance. Furthermore, managers need to observe the work of each person in the organization, closely related to salary, simultaneously based on each person’s performance. In conclusion, before any system is created, everyone should ensure that there is a good performance system and that the remuneration is proportional to the results (Ivanytska, Galayda& Tenytska,2018; Radvila&Silingiene,2020).

3.4 Organizational Effectiveness

The composition of people who form an independent business identity for a specific purpose is usually known as an organization and obtaining the desired result in the definition of resources is considered to be effective. Organizational effectiveness is the perception of the

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effectiveness of an organization in achieving the results that the organization wants to generate. It plays an important role in accelerating organizational development. It is the net satisfaction of all constituents in the process of collecting and converting inputs to outputs in an efficient manner (Ude,2019; Junaid, Athar,Khan, Sourat,Mehr,Nasee, Ullah, Shah, & Qazi,2020). Organizational effectiveness is defined as the extent to which an organization, by using a particular resource, meets its objectives without depleting its resources and without placing undue pressure on its employees. It is the maximum combined utility of the major constituents. The goal model describes the effectiveness of an organization in terms of the extent to which the organization achieves its objectives. The legitimacy model takes into account the effectiveness of the organization in terms of background assessment of component priorities for performance and the natural limits on performance from the perspective of the external environment (Pedersen& Johannsen,2018;Abdulai, Sawaneh & Kamara,2019). The system resource model defines an organization’s effectiveness in terms of its bargaining position in the organization, as shown in the organization’s ability, either in absolute or relative terms, to exploit its environment in the acquisition of limited and valuable resources and how they use these resources. This study aimed to determine the factors that increase employee motivation and the relationship of organizational effectiveness with employee motivation (Feraro-Banta& Shaikh,2019;Salsabila,Fakhri,Silvianita,Wardhana& Saragih,2020).

4. Conceptual Framework

4.1 Independent Variables

- Job Motivation
- Communication and Work Relationship
- Salary and Remuneration
-

4.2 Dependent Variable

- Organization Effectiveness

4.3 Hypothesis Development

H1. There is significant relationship between job motivations on organization effectiveness.

H2. There is significant relationship between communication and work relationship on organization effectiveness

H3. There is significant relationship salary and remuneration on organization effectiveness.

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Participants

The data was collected from 28 electrical manufacturing firms, 6822 employees, 361 questionnaires were distributed, and 222 questionnaires were analyzed among the employees (Krejcie and Morgan schedule, 1970). The respondents were selected using the stratified sampling technique.

5.2 Measurement Scale

Questionnaires are designed in Linkert Scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, and Strongly Agree).

5.3 Data Analysis

The data obtained were studied using SmartPLS version 3.7.8 to discuss the findings obtained. Statistical scholars highly recommend SmartPLS in producing an accurate analysis of each variable's cause and effect relationship. SmartPLS is also a sizeable multivariate analysis technique in social and psychological research. In addition, SmartPLS can analyze measurement model evaluation and structural model evaluation.

Table 1 shows the Loading, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for each construct studied; and the lowest value is **0.5237**, and the highest value is **0.5700**. These values are more significant than 0.5 (> 0.5), confirming that the study construct can explain the mean change of variance within the items (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Gefen & Straub, 2005; Henseler, Ringle & Sinkovics, 2009).

Table 1 , Loading, CR & AVE Results

	<i>Loading</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>AVE</i>
Job Motivation		0.8843	0.5237
JM1	0.7233		
JM2	0.7815		
JM3	0.8095		
JM4	0.6849		

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JM5	0.7528		
JM7	0.6415		
JM8	0.6552		
Communication and Work Relationship		0.9134	0.5700
CW1	0.7604		
CW2	0.8160		
CW3	0.8082		
CW4	0.7068		
CW5	0.7814		
CW6	0.6902		
CW7	0.6619		
CW8	0.7092		
Salary and Remuneration		0.8891	0.5362
SR1	0.6693		
SR2	0.6990		
SR3	0.7525		
SR4	0.8188		
SR5	0.8076		
SR6	0.7509		
SR7	0.6032		
SR8	0.		
Employees' Productivity		0.9122	0.5662
EP1	0.7313		
EP2	0.6628		
EP3	0.6958		
EP4	0.7904		

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EP5	0.7849
EP6	0.8312
EP7	0.7935
EP8	0.7144

Figure 1: Structural Model Direct Effects

The discriminate validity test was measured through two methods, namely the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion test and cross-loading (Henseler et al., 2009). Table 2 below shows the output from the HTMT analysis. The results can be calculated easily using the formula as in (Henseler, Ringle&Sarstedt, 2015).

**Table 2
Discriminate Validity**

Constructs	CW	EP	JM	SR
CW	0.7550			
EP	0.5437	0.7525		

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JM	0.4757	0.5925	0.7237	
SR	0.5837	0.6216	0.5196	0.7322

Note: Values in Bold face are the square root values of average variance extracted

5.4 Assessment of Structural Model

The findings for testing this direct effect model using SmartPLS software package version 3.7.8 through the structural equation model. This measurement aims to test the direct effect model and the effective model of the mediated variable. Therefore, empirical evidence has been used to construct a direct effect model, as shown in Figure 3.

Table 3
Summary of Hypotheses

<i>Relationship</i>	<i>Summary of Hypotheses</i>				
	beta	Std Error	T-Value	P-Value	Decision
JM->EP	0.3191	0.0808	4.0178	0.0000	Significant
CW->EP	0.2004	0.0918	2.0636	0.0000	Significant
SR->EP	0.3441	0.0765	4.4750	0.0000	Significant

6. Result

6.1 Job Motivation

The results obtained showed that job motivation variable significantly affects organizational effectiveness ($\beta = 0.3191$; $t = 4.0178$; $p = 0.0000$). H1 Accepted. The results also showed that job motivation contributed 32.4% ($R^2 = 0.324$) to organizational effectiveness.

6.2 Communication and Work Relationship

The results obtained showed that communication and work relationship variable significantly affects organizational effectiveness ($\beta = 0.0918$; $t = 2.0636$; $p = 0.0000$). H2 Accepted. The results also showed that communication and work relationship contributed 18.9% ($R^2 = 0.189$) to organizational effectiveness.

6.3 Salary and Remuneration

The results obtained showed that salary and remuneration variable significantly affects organizational effectiveness ($\beta = 0.0765$; $t = 4.4750$; $p = 0.0000$). H3 Accepted. The results

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also showed that salary and remuneration contributed 34.2% ($R^2=0.342$) to organizational effectiveness.

7. Conclusion

The result found that there is a significant relationship between job motivation on organizational effectiveness. Motivation refers to how driven and happy an employee is in their role. If an employee is motivated, they are more likely to do a good job and work hard. Motivation is very important for attracting employees, retaining employees, and general levels of productivity in a business. Having a motivated workforce has a range of advantages, such as lower levels of absenteeism, retention of employees and low levels of employee turnover, improved relations between management and employees, improved employees' performance, improved quality, and improved customer service. The result stated that employees whose work motivation is particularly high. They are probably working at a faster pace, responsibilities for their tasks, and spending time on their job. But most of all, they are focused and are putting any energy into their work. A motivated employee is enthusiastic, driven, and takes pride in their work. They accomplish tasks quickly, take action, and want to do a good job, both for themselves and for the organization. Whether their firm is at its best, or on its way up, employee motivation is very important. The moment it drops, revenue and output could soon follow. The motivation of employees is capable of supporting the growth of firms and organization effectiveness.

The result found that there is a significant relationship between communication and work relationships on organizational effectiveness. Effective communication is critical to any organization and can help it in many ways. Communication plays a role in product development, customer relations, and employee management – virtually every facet of a business's operations. Employees are a key audience because they often serve as the conduit to other audiences. If employees are informed and engaged, communications with other constituencies are likely to be strong as well. Effective communications help to establish clear expectations for employees and, perhaps surprisingly, for customers as well. For employees, clear expectations conveyed how their performance impacted the company and give them an indication of what they need to do to achieve positive feedback. For customers, clear communication can help manage their expectations about service issues or even about how best to interact with the organization. The finding also found that Effective communication builds strong relationships. Trust and loyalty are key factors in any relationship and both are boosted by communication that is focused on meeting individual needs, conveying important information, and providing feedback, positive and constructive. Strong relationships with external audiences also build strong solid communication about products, services, and organization culture and values. The result stated that Effective organizational communication leads to strong teamwork and the ability of employees at all levels of the organization to work together to achieve company goals. In addition, effective organizational communication provided employees the knowledge, structure, and positive

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work environment they need to feel comfortable dealing with conflict and resolving issues effectively.

The finding showed that there is a significant relationship between salary and remuneration on organizational effectiveness. The compensation and benefits are very important in increasing the employee motivation to perform well. This is because; it can improve the lives of the employee and secure their life in the future. The employees raised their performance so that they get the best salary and remuneration or promotion as the compensation and benefit based on the results of the work that has been done. In today's globalized world, organizations are facing changes generated by increased competition, mergers and acquisitions, shifting markets, and changing employee demographics. Therefore, an organization must strategize its competitive and benefits plan to attract and retain appropriate talent, maximize return on human capital and increase employees' job satisfaction. Salary and remuneration are powerful communicators of organizational goals and organizations reward employees for contributions that are consistent with organizational goals. Humans are naturally inclined to perform better when they perceive that they got sufficient payment or returns from their efforts. The present study analyzed the link between salary satisfaction, motivation, and remuneration on organizational effectiveness. Through this, the impact of employee compensation on achieving organizational goals was worked out. The study highlights that effective compensation management strikes a good balance between pay and work, thereby impacting organizational effectiveness.

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